

Synthesis of Quaternary Salts of Ammonia from Aromatic Aldehydes via Leuckart Reaction and their Plant Growth Retardant Activity

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Bach¹ prepared *N,N*-dimethylamines from cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone, cyclooctanone, cyclodecanone, acetophenone and from various acyclic ketones via Leuckart reaction. He found that yield decreases when high substituted acyclic ketones are subjected to this reaction. Here we have prepared *N,N*-dimethylamines (**2a-d**) from benzaldehyde, anisaldehyde, 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde and salicyldehyde respectively, by heating the aldehyde with DMF and HCOOH (85%). Benzaldehyde produced *N,N*-dimethylbenzylamine (**2a**) in a low yield (25%). The yield was slightly improved with the introduction of hydroxyl group in the *ortho*-position, i.e. *N,N*-dimethyl-*o*-hydroxybenzylamine (**2c**) was prepared from salicyldehyde (**1d**) in 30% yield. However, *N,N*-dimethyl-*p*-methoxybenzylamine (**2b**) was prepared from anisaldehyde (**1b**) in 40% yield and *N,N*-dimethyl-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzylamine (**2c**) from 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (**1c**) in 45% yield. The presence of *N,N*-dimethylamino group in **2a-d** was confirmed by a singlet for six protons at δ 2.15–2.4 in their pmr spectra. Their ir spectra showed a characteristic signal of *N,N*-dimethylamino group² at 2780 cm⁻¹ and complete elimination of carbonyl peak. The tertiary amines (**2a-d**) obtained were then refluxed with ethyl bromide and methyl iodide in dry acetone³ separately to get the quaternary salts of the amine (**3a-d**, **4a-d**) in good yields.

The quaternary salts were then tested as plant growth retardants on turnip seeds⁴ (Table 1). All the salts showed plant growth retarding activity but less than that of ABA. However, compounds **3a**, **4a**, and **4c** showed comparable activity to that of ABA at 100 ppm.

Experimental

B.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃/CCl₄) were recorded on a EM-390/360 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer.

N,N-Dimethylarylamine. General procedure : A mix-

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF QUATERNARY SALTS OF AMMONIA ON TURNIP SEED GERMINATION AFTER 60 h

Compd. no.	% germination [*]				Seedling length (av., cm)			
	10	25	50	100 mg dm ⁻³	10	25	50	100 mg dm ⁻³
3a	50	26	12	6	0.69	0.25	0.12	0.05
4a	64	46	38	28	0.80	0.72	0.46	0.40
3b	76	70	60	56	0.89	0.81	0.63	0.56
4b	80	75	70	66	0.85	0.80	0.68	0.59
3c	92	88	72	68	0.93	0.83	0.77	0.60
4c	73	69	61	42	0.58	0.50	0.34	0.15
3d	88	83	76	72	1.11	0.92	0.61	0.72
4d	85	79	75	64	1.03	0.83	0.62	0.51
CD at 5% (compound)				A = 0.1603				0.0518
CD at 5% (concentration)				B = 0.1133				0.0366
CD at (compound × concentration)				A × B = 0.3205				0.1036
Control :	% ermination				Seedlings length (av., cm)			
ABA (5 mg dm ⁻³)	16				0.34			
Water	100				1.77			

*Average of 50 seeds

ture of aromatic aldehyde (0.06 mol), dimethyl formamide (14.6 ml) and formic acid (7 ml; 85%) was heated at 190° for 6 h. The resulting pale yellow homogeneous solution was added slowly to 10% HCl (50 ml) and the aqueous amine hydrochloride was washed several times with ether. The aqueous phase was treated with 30% NaOH (basic to litmus) and the product was extracted with ethyl ether. The ethereal layer was dried (Na₂SO₄) and the residue was vacuum distilled to give the tertiary amines : N,N-dimethylbenzylamine⁵ (2a; 2.5 g, 25%), b.p. 150–55°/29–30 mm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3450, 2950, 2780, 2410, 1600, 1500, 1425, 1330, 1230, 1000, 930 and 830 cm⁻¹; δ 2.25 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.3 (2H, s, CH₂N(CH₃)₂), 6.45–7.1 (5H, ArH); N,N-dimethyl-4-methoxybenzylamine⁵ (2b; 4 g, 40%), b.p. 130–35°/4–5 mm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3480, 2980, 2780, 1500, 1445, 1300, 1220, 1110, 1010, 970, 900 and 820 cm⁻¹; δ 2.15 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.33 (2H, s, CH₂N(CH₃)₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.6–7.3 (4H, ArH); N,N-dimethyl-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzylamine⁶ (2c; 6 g, 45%), a thickoily liquid; $\nu_{\max}$ 3400, 2950, 2780, 1590, 1500, 1410, 1320, 1210, 1130, 1000, 890 and 820 cm⁻¹; δ 2.3 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.45 (2H, s, CH₂N(CH₃)₂), 3.9 (9H, s, 3 × OCH₃), 6.7 (2H, ArH); N,N-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzylamine (2d; 2.71 g, 30%), a thick oil, $\nu_{\max}$ 3300, 2850, 2780, 1610, 1560, 1300, 1250, 1100, 1050, 980, 930 and 790 cm⁻¹; δ 2.23 (1H, s, OH), 2.4 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.55 (2H, s, CH₂N(CH₃)₂), 6.9–7.4 (4H, ArH).

Quaternary salts. General procedure : The tertiary amine (500 mg) dissolved in dry acetone (10 ml) was

refluxed with excess of alkyl halide on water-bath for 4 h. Removal of solvent afforded quaternary salts of ammonia : 3a, thick oil (0.8 g, 85%); 4a, crystalline solid (0.85 g, 80%), m.p. 154–55°; 3b, thick oil (0.51 g, 65%); 4b, white crystalline solid (0.7 g, 80%), m.p. 78–79°; 3c, yellow coloured crystalline solid (0.6 g, 80%), m.p. 39–40°; 4c, white solid (0.73 g, 90%), m.p. 160–61°; 3d, thick oil (0.69 g, 80%); 4d, crystalline solid (0.82 g, 85%) m.p. 110–12°.

Plant growth retardant activities : Fifty seeds of turnip (*Brassica rapa*, Var. L₁) in three replications were placed on a filter paper laid on the bottom of a petri dish (9 cm dia) and to which the test solutions (5 ml) of different concentrations (10, 25, 50 or 100 ppm) of the compounds were poured. Each dish was kept at 28 ± 1° for 60 h and thereafter, the percent seed germination and seedling lengths were recorded. Separate control treatment with ABA (5 ppm) and water was also recorded simultaneously.

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